

Interview Protocol

Context and general vision of the project/organization

1. Is your organization considered an Agile organization? And your project?
2. What are the Agile methodology(ies) adopted by your team?
3. What is the working model currently adopted (remote, hybrid, in-person) by your organization? Does your project follow the same positioning?
4. Was this work model already adopted before the Covid-19 pandemic that began in 2020?
5. Do you believe that your organization's culture was impacted by these changes? In what way?

Identifying the characteristics of feedback processes in the projects/organization

6. Does your organization's culture support feedback? Is feedback already a practice adopted by your team/organization?
7. Does the organization provide support and guidelines regarding the adoption of feedback, or are all feedback processes implemented in isolation by teams?
8. In general, how is the feedback process carried out in your team?
9. How often is feedback given to individuals?
10. What are the main steps and results obtained from the feedback process for your team?
11. Does your team/organization use any tools to support the feedback process?
12. Does the feedback process used include the entire team or just leader-team member?

Identifying topics considered main challenges/difficulties faced while adopting a feedback process

13. What are the main difficulties or challenges faced during the feedback process in your team?
14. Do you consider that there are differences between the challenges faced during feedback in the remote and in-person work model? What would they be?

Identifying main benefits acquired from feedback process adoption

15. What are the main benefits obtained by your team from the feedback process?
16. Do you consider that changes in the work model have had an impact on the repercussions of these benefits? In what way?
17. What are the main changes/results obtained by practicing feedback within your team?

Recommendations to improve the feedback process

18. In general, what are the main positive points that the practice of feedback can bring to software development teams?
19. In general, what are the main negative points that the practice of feedback can bring to software development teams?
20. In your opinion, what are the best practices or recommendations that an Agile team should follow to have good results when adopting a feedback process?
21. Do you have any additional considerations to add?